

D2.3 – Benchmark data for domain-specific and non-regression performance tests

Version 1.0

GA no 952165

Dissemination Level

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | PU: Public |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) |

Document Information

Project Title	Targeting Real Chemical accuracy at the EXascale
Project Acronym	TREX
Grant Agreement No	952165
Instrument	Call: H2020-INFRAEDI-2019-1
Topic	INFRAEDI-05-2020 Centres of Excellence in EXascale computing
Start Date of Project	01-10-2020
Duration of Project	36 Months
Project Website	https://trex-coe.eu/

Deliverable Number	D2.3
Deliverable title	Benchmark data for domain-specific and non-regression performance tests
Due Date	M12 – 30-09-2021
Actual Submission Date	28-09-2021

Work Package	WP2 – Code modularization and interfacing
Lead Author (Org)	Cédric Valensi (UVSQ)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Kévin Camus (UVSQ)
Reviewers (Org)	Sandro Sorella (SISSA); Pablo de Oliveira (UVSQ); Jan Beerens (UT)
Version	1.0
Dissemination level	Public
Nature	Open Research Data Pilot
Draft / final	Final
No. of pages including cover	28

Disclaimer

TREX: Targeting Real Chemical Accuracy at the Exascale project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 952165

The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Versioning

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
1.0	28-09-2021	Cédric Valensi (UVSQ)	First Official Release

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
UT	UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS
SISSA	SCUOLA INTERNAZIONALE SUPERIORE DI STUDI AVANZATI DI TRIESTE
CINECA	CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO
FZJ	FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JULICH GMBH
MPG	MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV
UVSQ	UNIVERSITE DE VERSAILLES SAINT-QUENTIN-EN-YVELINES.
Megware	MEGWARE COMPUTER VERTRIEB UND SERVICE GMBH
STUBA	SLOVENSKA TECHNICKA UNIVERZITA V BRATISLAVE
UNIVIE	UNIVERSITAT WIEN
TUL	POLITECHNIKA LODZKA
TRUST-IT	TRUST-IT SRL

Table of Contents

Document Information	1
Disclaimer.....	2
Versioning	3
Abbreviations	4
Table of Figures.....	7
Table of Tables	8
1 Introduction	1
2 Deliverable content.....	1
3 Reference values.....	2
3.1 Self-consistency checks	2
3.2 Comparison with previous results.....	2
4 Performance reports.....	2
4.1 Navigating report repository.....	3
4.1.1 Examples of report paths.....	4
4.2 Analysing reports.....	4
4.2.1 Experiment configuration	5
4.2.2 Comparison reports	6
4.2.3 Scalability reports.....	6
5 Adding new benchmarks.....	8
References	9
Appendix A: Benchmarks	I
5.1 CHAMP.....	I
5.1.1 Sources.....	I
5.1.2 Datasets.....	I
5.1.3 Compilation.....	I
5.1.4 Execution.....	I
5.1.5 Reference outputs	I
5.1.6 Sample timings.....	I
5.1.7 Performance reports.....	II
5.1.8 Analysing with MAQAO.....	II
5.2 GAMMCOR	II
5.2.1 Sources.....	II

5.2.2	Datasets.....	II
5.2.3	Compilation.....	II
5.2.4	Execution.....	III
5.2.5	Sample timing.....	III
5.2.6	Performance reports.....	III
5.2.7	Analysing with MAQAO.....	III
5.3	NECI.....	III
5.3.1	Sources.....	III
5.3.2	Datasets.....	III
5.3.3	Compilation.....	III
5.3.4	Execution.....	IV
5.3.5	Reference time.....	IV
5.3.6	Performance reports.....	IV
5.3.7	Analysing with MAQAO.....	IV
5.4	QMC=CHEM.....	IV
5.4.1	Sources.....	IV
5.4.2	Datasets.....	IV
5.4.3	Compilation.....	V
5.4.4	Execution.....	V
5.4.5	Sample timing.....	V
5.4.6	Performance reports.....	V
5.4.7	Analysing with MAQAO.....	V
5.5	TURBORVB.....	V
5.5.1	Sources.....	V
5.5.2	Datasets.....	V
5.5.3	Compilation.....	V
5.5.4	Execution.....	VI
5.5.5	Reference outputs.....	VI
5.5.6	Sample timing.....	VI
5.5.7	Performance reports.....	VI
5.5.8	Analysing with MAQAO.....	VI
Appendix B:	Analysing a benchmark with MAQAO.....	VII
Appendix C:	Reports list.....	VIII

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Global metrics of a MAQAO performance report.....	4
Figure 2: Summary of the conditions under which a performance analysis report was generated	5
Figure 3: Global metrics comparison across different MAQAO performance reports.....	6
Figure 4: Global metrics of a MAQAO scalability performance report	7

Table of Tables

No table of figures entries found.

1 Introduction

One of the main goals of the TREX project is the implementation of optimised libraries for QMC computation (QMCKI) and I/O for interoperability and synergic applications of TREX codes as well as for use by other software packages outside TREX. A key ingredient to successfully accomplish the above target is ensuring that the libraries do provide an improvement in terms of performance, and not at the expense of accuracy. Also, since development is an ongoing process, it is vital to be able to detect early on if a new update caused regressions, in term of accuracy, performance or stability.

To address this concern, a set of benchmarks has been compiled. These benchmarks are intended to offer high-level tests, executable by users of the QMCKI or I/O libraries in order to check their installation as well as by developers of these libraries to detect any regression in terms of accuracy or performance. They will also allow to monitor the overall evolution of performance during the development of the libraries.

The present document is intended as a short user guide to this set of benchmarks. Its purpose is to describe how to exploit it along with the associated repository of performance reports, and how to add new benchmarks to the set.

Chapter 2 recaps the content of the deliverable, chapter 3 defines how to use reference values for checking the benchmark results, chapter 4 presents the performance reports, and chapter 5 describes the necessary elements to provide for adding another benchmark to the list.

Appendix A: presents the list of benchmarks, along with all necessary information for executing and analysing them. Appendix B: describes how to generate a performance analysis report for a benchmark. Finally, Appendix C: presents the correspondence between the existing reports and the benchmarks versions.

2 Deliverable content

The deliverable is composed of the following elements:

- A list of benchmark applications and all associated information, which include:
 - Datasets
 - Reference values (if applicable)
- A repository of performance reports
- The present document, which describes
 - The main goals of non-regression tests
 - How to navigate the performance reports repository
 - How to use the performance reports to observe performance evolution
 - For each benchmark
 - How to access its sources and compile it
 - How to execute it
 - How to check its values
 - How to generate performance reports
 - How to add new benchmarks to the list

3 Reference values

If applicable, each benchmark must offer a way to check its return values through one of the following methods:

- Self-consistency checks
- Comparison with results from previous tests
- Comparison with expected results

3.1 Self-consistency checks

This method consists in the benchmark checking its own results and displaying an error message or returning an error code if they are not identified as valid. The method for checking is left at the benchmark developers' choice.

If this option is not implemented in the benchmark from the start, another method will be used for checking the validity of results. No additional implementation will be requested from the benchmarks' developers.

3.2 Comparison with previous results

This method consists in comparing the results of the benchmarks with a reference established from a previous execution. The reference results will be included in the same repository as the one containing the benchmark or the datasets (if different).

In some cases, it may be necessary to handle differences between the results and the reference on non-significant digits, which can happen for either of the following causes:

- Variability of results: depending on how some results are computed, floating point values may not be entirely identical from one run to another.
- Difference by hardware: because of the difference in handling floating-point values from one hardware architecture to another, the results may vary depending on the platform on which the run is executed.

These differences can be handled through either of the following methods:

- Define a different reference file per architecture.
- Use an automated way such as a script to perform the comparison between results and their reference, which will include a tolerance margin specifying for each numerical value the percentage of error authorised before triggering an error.

It is possible that future performance optimisations of kernels for which a low number of significant digits suffice will involve reducing precision (such trade-offs will be explored in the context of task *T3.3 Reproducibility and numerical portability* thanks to dedicated tools). The comparison with the reference will need to take this kind of evolution into account for the concerned benchmarks.

4 Performance reports

The performance reports are hosted on an online repository. Since they come in the form of HTML files, they can be accessed with any browser.

4.1 Navigating report repository

The report repository root is accessible either at [3] (for reports on public codes) or [4] (for reports on private codes).

The path of a report below the root provides information about the benchmark involved, the dataset used, and the conditions of the analysis. It is built as follows:

```
[ROOT]/[NAME]/[VARIANT]/[DATASET]/[ARCH]/[LEVEL]/[NAME]_[VARIANT]_[DATASET]_[ARCH]-[ISET]_o[OMP_THREADS]_m[MPITASKS]_c[CORES]_[LEVEL]_[INFO]
```

with:

- [ROOT]: Root of the report repository
- [NAME]: Name of the benchmark
- [VARIANT]: Name of the benchmark variant
- [DATASET]: Name of the dataset
- [ARCH]: Name of the hardware architecture on which the report was generated
- [ISET]: (Optional) name of the instruction set for which the benchmark was compiled
- [OMP_THREADS]: Number of OpenMP threads
- [MPITASKS]: Number of MPI tasks
- [CORES]: Number of cores
- [LEVEL]: Report level (written as ov1, ov2, ov3, ...)
- [INFO]: Extra information for specific runs

In the case of scalability reports (cf. 4.2.3), `OMP_THREADS` and `MPITASKS` will have multiple values separated by a dash (-).

In the case of comparison reports, (cf. 4.2.2), `VARIANT`, `DATASET`, `ARCH` and `ISET` will have multiple values separated by a dash (-) depending on the differences between the compared reports. `INFO` will contain additional information about the differences between the compared reports if they are not covered by another field (e.g. compiler options).

4.1.1 Examples of report paths

- https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/public_html/oneview2020/TURBORVB/31augnewrefactorization/vmc/skl/ov1/TURBORVB_31augrefactorization_vmc_skl_o1_m1_c1_ov1: Report level 1 (ov1) for variant 31augnewrefactorization of benchmark TurboRVB, executed with dataset vmc on a Skylake, with one MPI process and one OpenMP thread on one core.
- https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/public_html/oneview2020/TURBORVB/compare/TURBORVB_31augnewrefactorization-08julyrefactorization_fn_skl_o1_m1_c1_ov1_compare/ : Comparison of reports level 1 for variants 31augnewrefactorization and 08julyrefactorization of benchmark TurboRVB, executed with dataset fn on a Skylake, with one MPI process and one OpenMP thread on one core.
- https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/public_html/oneview2020/GAMMCOR/gammcor1-4/SHORT/skl/ov1/GAMMCOR_gammcor1-4_SHORT_skl_o1-2-4-8-16-26-52_m1_c1_ov1_scala-compact_prompt/ : Scalability report level 1 for variant gammcor1-4 or benchmark GAMMCOR, executed with dataset SHORT on a Skylake, with one MPI process on one core, and OpenMP threads taking values 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 26 and 52, using compact thread affinity and containing additional OpenMP analysis using MAQAO module PROMPT.

4.2 Analysing reports

The reports present a detailed analysis of the performance of the application and the main bottlenecks. A complete description of the information contained in these reports can be found on [1].

Global Metrics		?
Total Time (s)		481.84
Profiled Time (s)		481.84
Time in analyzed loops (%)		18.51
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)		13.1
Time in user code (%)		25.35
Compilation Options		OK
Perfect Flow Complexity		1.01
Array Access Efficiency (%)		83.97
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread		1.00
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution		1.00
No Scalar Integer	Potential Speedup	1.06
	Nb Loops to get 80%	12
FP Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.04
	Nb Loops to get 80%	12
Fully Vectorised	Potential Speedup	1.17
	Nb Loops to get 80%	19
FP Arithmetic Only	Potential Speedup	1.11
	Nb Loops to get 80%	16

Figure 1: Global metrics of a MAQAO performance report

The *Global Metrics* panel on the Global tab contains general quality metrics quantifying the performance of the code. For the purpose of non-regression performance tests, the “Total Time” metric can be used to compare time with previous versions. This can be done automatically using comparison reports (see 4.2.2).

4.2.1 Experiment configuration

The Experiment Summary panel on the Global tab summarises the conditions of execution of the benchmark. In particular, the “Compilation Options” line specifies the name and version of the compiler, along with the main options used. This can be useful for cases where the purpose of the benchmark analysis is identifying the impact of a modification in the compilation chain, or to reproduce an existing analysis with the exact same conditions.

Experiment Summary ?			
Application	/home/kcamus/Trex/turborvb /tmp/workload_TurboRVB/bin/turborvb-serial.x		
Timestamp	2021-09-06 11:06:30	Universal Timestamp	1630919190
Number of processes observed	1	Number of threads observed	1
Experiment Type	Sequential		
Machine	skylake		
Model Name	Intel(R) Xeon(R) Platinum 8170 CPU @ 2.10GHz		
Architecture	x86_64	Micro Architecture	SKYLAKE
Cache Size	36608 KB	Number of Cores	26
OS Version	Linux 5.12.8-arch1-1 #1 SMP PREEMPT Fri, 28 May 2021 15:10:20 +0000		
Architecture used during static analysis	x86_64	Micro Architecture used during static analysis	SKYLAKE
Compilation Options	turborvb-serial.x: Intel 2021.2.0 -i./... -qopenmp -fpp -ip -fno-common -O3 -DMKL -g -xCORE- AVX512 -fno-omit-frame-pointer -lgfortran -c		

Figure 2: Summary of the conditions under which a performance analysis report was generated

4.2.2 Comparison reports

It is possible to generate a comparison report based on two or more reports. Some of these comparisons are already present in the report repository.

A comparison report displays side to side all available performance metrics from all compared reports. This makes them the easiest way of performing performance non-regression tests.

▼ Compared Reports			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> r1: turborvb_serial_31aug-new-refactorization_o1_ov1_fn_correctdataset r2: turborvb_serial_31aug-new-refactorization_o1_ov1_fn_correctdataset_loopcount7/ 			
Global Metrics ?			
Metric	r1	r2	
Total Time (s)	84.02	85.08	
Promoted time (s)	84.02	85.08	
Time in analyzed loops (%)	21.7	21.8	
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	12.7	11.6	
Time in user code (%)	31.0	31.1	
Compilation Options	OK	OK	
Perfect Flow Complexity	1.01	1.01	
Array Access Efficiency (%)	74.3	69.6	
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.00	1.00	
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.00	1.00	
Potential Speedup	1.06	1.07	
No Scalar Integer			
Nb Loops to get 80%	15	14	
Potential Speedup	1.04	1.05	
FP Vectorised			
Nb Loops to get 80%	16	15	
Potential Speedup	1.22	1.23	
Fully Vectorised			
Nb Loops to get 80%	25	25	
Potential Speedup	1.11	1.11	
Only FP Arithmetic			
Nb Loops to get 80%	18	18	

Figure 3: Global metrics comparison across different MAQAO performance reports

4.2.3 Scalability reports

Scalability reports present the comparison between runs of the same benchmarks with differing number of threads. They can be useful for checking if performance has not regressed for certain number of threads.

The “Scalability – Speedup” metric presents the potential speed-up to be obtained if efficiency was perfect for each considered number of threads. It can be used to detect a regression in the way the code scales across different threads from one scalability report to another.

▼ Compared Reports

- r1: run_0
- r2: OMP_NUM_THREADS = 2
- r3: OMP_NUM_THREADS = 4
- r4: OMP_NUM_THREADS = 8
- r5: OMP_NUM_THREADS = 16
- r6: OMP_NUM_THREADS = 26
- r7: OMP_NUM_THREADS = 52

Global Metrics ?

Metric	r1	r2	r3	r4	r5	r6	r7
Total Time (s)	126.39	67.17	38.22	23.98	18.08	18.92	24.92
Profiled Time (s)	126.39	67.17	38.22	23.98	18.08	18.92	24.92
Time in analyzed loops (%)	23.4	22.4	20.5	17.3	12.6	9.03	5.13
Time in analyzed innermost loops (%)	10.3	9.70	9.31	7.73	5.80	3.79	2.06
Time in user code (%)	35.5	34.1	31.3	26.4	19.6	15.1	10.6
Compilation Options	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
Perfect Flow Complexity	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Array Access Efficiency (%)	78.8	80.1	80.6	79.8	80.4	79.8	80.9
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.06	1.07	1.19	1.68
Perfect OpenMP + MPI + Pthread + Perfect Load Distribution	1.00	1.07	1.18	1.41	1.70	2.03	3.04
No Scalar Integer							
Potential Speedup	1.05	1.04	1.04	1.03	1.03	1.02	1.02
Nb Loops to get 80%	8	8	9	9	10	8	7
FP Vectorised							
Potential Speedup	1.04	1.04	1.04	1.03	1.02	1.01	1.01
Nb Loops to get 80%	5	5	6	6	8	9	12
Fully Vectorised							
Potential Speedup	1.23	1.22	1.19	1.16	1.11	1.08	1.04
Nb Loops to get 80%	13	12	12	13	14	15	14
Only FP Arithmetic							
Potential Speedup	1.10	1.09	1.08	1.07	1.05	1.04	1.03
Nb Loops to get 80%	10	9	10	11	13	12	11
Scalability - Speedup	1.00	1.06	1.21	1.52	2.29	3.89	10.25

Figure 4: Global metrics of a MAQAO scalability performance report

5 Adding new benchmarks

The addition of a new benchmark to the list must include the following information:

- Repository containing the benchmark sources
- Pre-requisites: Description of the hardware and software configuration for running the test
 - Operating System
 - Processor version
 - Accelerator (GPU) if applicable
 - Compiler vendor
 - Required packages
 - MPI runtime
 - Job scheduler
 - Additional dependencies
- Description of the steps to perform to compile the benchmark, using a configure script, cmake or a similar system.
- List of parameters to pass to the application. If ran using a job scheduler, an example of job scheduler script must be provided.
- Repository containing the datasets for the benchmark.
- Any additional environment variables to set at execution.
- If applicable, the repository containing the reference values for each dataset.
- Variables to set in the MAQAO configuration script for analysing the benchmark.

References

- [1] MAQAO documentation <https://www.maqao.org/documentation.html> or <https://maqao.exascale-computing.eu/documentation.html>
- [2] MAQAO download: <https://www.maqao.org/downloads.html> or <https://maqao.exascale-computing.eu/download.html>
- [3] Public performance reports repository root https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/public_html/oneview2020/
- [4] Private performance reports repository root https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/private_html/oneview2020/
- [5] CHAMP sources repository <https://github.com/filippi-claudia/champ>
- [6] CHAMP dataset repository https://github.com/TREX-CoE/workload_champ
- [7] CHAMP performance reports root https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/private_html/oneview2020/CHAMP/
- [8] GAMMCOR sources repository <https://github.com/pernalk/GAMMCOR>
- [9] GAMMCOR dataset repository <https://gitlab.jsc.fz-juelich.de/trex/GammCor>
- [10] GAMMCOR performance reports root https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/public_html/oneview2020/GAMMCOR/
- [11] NECI public sources repository <https://github.com/TREX-CoE/neci>
- [12] NECI private sources repository https://bitbucket.org/neci_developers/neci/src/master/
- [13] NECI dataset repository https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/kguther/neci_performance_tests
- [14] NECI public performance reports root https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/public_html/oneview2020/NECI/
- [15] NECI private performance reports root https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/private_html/oneview2020/NECI/
- [16] QMC=CHEM sources repository <https://gitlab.com/scemama/qmcchem>
- [17] QMC=CHEM dataset repository https://gitlab.version.fz-juelich.de/trex/workload_qmcchem.git
- [18] QMC=CHEM performance reports root https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/public_html/oneview2020/QMCHEM/
- [19] TurboRVB sources repository https://github.com/TREX-CoE/workload_TurboRVB
- [20] TurboRVB dataset repository https://github.com/TREX-CoE/workload_TurboRVB
- [21] TurboRVB performance reports root https://datafront.maqao.exascale-computing.eu/public_html/oneview2020/TURBORVB/

Appendix A: Benchmarks

This appendix describes how to retrieve, compile, execute and analyse each benchmark.

Some of the command lines described below may change as the benchmarks evolve during the course of the project, causing for instance the compilation or execution commands to be different for more recent versions of the benchmarks. Addenda to this appendix will be released with the updated commands and the associated versions. The information presented here will remain relevant for executing older version of the codes for comparison purposes.

5.1 CHAMP

5.1.1 Sources

Available on [5].

Access to repository must be requested from Claudia Filippi (c.filippi@utwente.nl)

5.1.2 Datasets

Available from [6].

5.1.3 Compilation

Required software:

- Intel compiler
- cmake

Commands (additional information available in the documentation):

```
cmake -H. -Bbuild -DCMAKE_Fortran_COMPILER=mpiifort
cmake -build build - -j4
```

5.1.4 Execution

The executable is generated as `vmc.mov1` and is located in the `bin` directory.

The code must be launched from the chosen dataset directory:

```
mpirun -s all -np <num_processes> <path_to_binary> < <input file> >
<output file>
```

For test cases, input file is `vmc.inp` and output file `vmc.out_core<num_processes>`

5.1.5 Reference outputs

Reference outputs for each dataset are present in the same directory as the dataset. The name is identical to the output with an additional suffix corresponding to the platform for which the reference output applies.

5.1.6 Sample timings

Times observed on a Skylake (xeon8170@2.1GHz) on different datasets:

- **Base version:**
 - `butadiene_cipsi500_T_optWF` : 188 s

- butadiene_cipsi5k_T_optWF : 416 s
- butadiene_cipsi15k_T_optWF : 802 s
- **Dgemv** version:
 - butadiene_cipsi500_T_optWF : 135 s
 - butadiene_cipsi15k_T_optWF : 421 s

5.1.7 Performance reports

Performance reports for CHAMP are available under [7]

Access must be requested from Jäsper Salah Ibnamar (mohammed-salah.ibnamar@uvsq.fr) with validation from Claudia Filippi (c.filippi@utwente.nl).

5.1.8 Analysing with MAQAO

Variables to set in the MAQAO configuration file:

- `binary`: full path to the executable
- `dataset`: full path to the chosen dataset
- `run_command`: `<binary> <vmc.inp> vmc.out_core1`
- `number_processes`: number of required processes.
- `mpi_command`: `"mpirun -s all -np <number_processes>"`

5.2 GAMMCOR

5.2.1 Sources

Available on [8].

5.2.2 Datasets

Available from [9]

Access to repository requires the following steps:

- Create a JSC (web services) account following instructions at <http://gitlab.pages.jsc.fz-juelich.de/ldap/>
- Attempt authentication to the Gitlab server by connecting to <https://gitlab.version.fz-juelich.de/trex>. (this will return an authorisation error access but is necessary to register the account on the Gitlab server)
- Request to be added to the TREX group from Dirk Pleiter (d.pleiter@fz-juelich.de).

5.2.3 Compilation

Required software:

- Intel compiler
- cmake

Main commands (additional information available in the documentation):


```
mkdir OBJ
cd xcfun && make
cd .. && make
```

5.2.4 Execution

The executable is generated as `gammcor` and is located in the `main` directory.

The code must be launched from the chosen dataset directory:

```
OMP_NUM_THREADS=<number_of_threads> <path_to_binary>
```

Input files are named `input.inp`. They do not need to be specified on the command line.

5.2.5 Sample timing

Times observed on a Skylake (xeon8170@2.1GHz) on different datasets:

- **Base** version:
 - SHORT: 1001 s
 - LONG: 12126 s
- **Scemama** version:
 - SHORT: 639 s
 - LONG: 5485 s

5.2.6 Performance reports

Performance reports for GAMMCOR are available under

5.2.7 Analysing with MAQAO

Variables to set in the MAQAO configuration file:

- `binary`: full path to the executable
- `dataset`: full path to the chosen dataset
- `run_command`: `<binary>`
- `omp_num_threads`: number of required OpenMP threads.

5.3 NECI

5.3.1 Sources

Available on [11].

Also on [12] after request from Oskar Weser (o.weser@fkf.mpg.de).

5.3.2 Datasets

Available on [13] after request from Werner Dobrautz (w.dobrautz@fkf.mpg.de).

5.3.3 Compilation

Required software:

- Intel compiler

- hdf5 (can be compiled along with NECI if not present)

Main commands (additional information available in the documentation):

```
mkdir build
cd build
cmake .. -DCMAKE_C_COMPILER=icc -DCMAKE_CXX_COMPILER=icpc -
DCMAKE_Fortran_COMPILER=ifort -DMPI_C_COMPILER=mpicc -
DMPI_CXX_COMPILER=mpicxx
make
```

5.3.4 Execution

The executable is generated as `neci` and is located in the `build/bin` directory.

The code must be launched from the chosen dataset directory:

```
OMP_NUM_THREADS=<num_threads> mpirun -np <num_processes>
<path_to_binary> input > output
```

5.3.5 Reference time

Times observed on a Skylake (xeon8170@2.1GHz) are on the order of 300 s for all datasets.

5.3.6 Performance reports

Performance reports for NECI are available under [14]

Performance reports corresponding to versions present on the bitbucket repository are available under [15]

Access to these must be requested from Jäsper Salah Ibnamar (mohammed-salah.ibnamar@uvsq.fr) with validation from Oskar Weser (o.weser@fkf.mpg.de).

5.3.7 Analysing with MAQAO

Variables to set in the MAQAO configuration file:

- `binary`: full path to the executable
- `dataset`: full path to the chosen dataset
- `run_command`: "`<binary> input > output`"
- `number_processes`: number of required processes.
- `omp_num_threads`: number of required OpenMP threads.
- `mpi_command`: "`mpirun -np <number_processes>`"

5.4 QMC=CHEM

5.4.1 Sources

Available on [16].

5.4.2 Datasets

Available on [17]

5.4.3 Compilation

Required software:

- Intel compiler
- cmake
- QP (installed from <https://github.com/QuantumPackage/qp2>)

Main commands (additional information available in the documentation or from Anthony Scemama (scemama@irsamc.ups-tlse.fr)):

```
cp make.config.ifort make.config file
source qmcchemrc && make
```

5.4.4 Execution

The executable is generated as `qmc`, with the `ocaml qmcchem` as its launcher.

The code must be launched from the chosen dataset directory:

```
<path_to_binary> run <path_to_dataset>
```

5.4.5 Sample timing

Times observed on a Skylake (xeon8170@2.1GHz) on different datasets:

- Benzene: 585 s

5.4.6 Performance reports

Performance reports for QMC=CHEM are available under [18].

5.4.7 Analysing with MAQAO

Variables to set in the MAQAO configuration file:

- `binary`: full path to the `qmc` executable
- `dataset`: full path to the chosen dataset
- `run_command`: `<binary> run dataset_name`

5.5 TURBORVB

5.5.1 Sources

Available on [19].

5.5.2 Datasets

Available on [20].

The three main datasets are available from `workload_TurboRVB/test_juwels` and are `fnc`, `fn` and `vmc`.

5.5.3 Compilation

Required software:

- Intel compiler

Main commands (additional information available in the documentation):

Copy and edit the file corresponding to the architecture from the config directory, e.g.:

```
cp config/make.inc.intel19_ubuntu18 make.inc
cp src/make.txt_standard src/make.txt
```

For compiling the serial version of the code and the necessary tools for analysing the output execute the following script:

```
./makeall
```

For the MPI parallel version instead:

```
./makempi
```

5.5.4 Execution

The executable is generated as `turborvb-mpi.x` for the MPI version and as `turborvb-serial.x` for the serial version.

The code must be launched from the `test_juwels` directory with the command:

```
OMP_NUM_THREADS=<num_threads> mpirun -np <num_processes>
<path_to_binary> <input file> > <output file>
```

Input files for datasets `fn`, `fnc` and `vmc` are named respectively `datasfn.input`, `datasfnc.input` and `datasvmc.input`.

5.5.5 Reference outputs

Reference outputs are available in files `REFERENCE_XXI`, `REFERENCE_XXI_HOKUSAY`, and `REFERENCE_XXI_marconi100`.

5.5.6 Sample timing

Times observed on a Skylake (xeon8170@2.1GHz) on different datasets:

- **fn:** 118 s
- **fnc:** 544 s
- **vmc:** 137 s

5.5.7 Performance reports

Performance reports for TurboRVB are available under [21].

5.5.8 Analysing with MAQAO

Variables to set in the MAQAO configuration file:

- `binary`: full path to the executable
- `dataset`: full path to the directory containing datasets
- `run_command`: `<binary> < dataset_file > out_file`
- `number_processes`: number of required processes.
- `omp_num_threads`: number of required OpenMP threads.
- `mpi_command`: `"mpirun -np <number_processes>"`

Appendix B: Analysing a benchmark with MAQAO

The latest version of the MAQAO performance analysis tool can be retrieved from [2].

MAQAO uses a configuration file specifying the parameters of the analysis and the necessary information on how to launch the application.

Command line for generating a report:

```
maqao oneview -R1 -c=config.lua xp=path_to_report_directory
```

Command line for generating a comparison report from existing reports:

```
maqao oneview --compare-reports -inputs=report1,report2,report3,...
```

Additional information on the use of MAQAO can be found in [1].

Appendix C: Reports list

The array below presents for each benchmark the version associated to the existing reports. It will be supplemented by addenda that will be released as reports corresponding to future versions of the benchmarks are added to the repository.

The path to each report on the repository obeys the rules described in 4.1.

The column *Benchmark* corresponds to element NAME in the tree structure (unless noted otherwise in the *Notes* column).

The column *Variant Name* corresponds to element VARIANT in the tree structure.

The *Commit* column specifies the version. By default, all the codes were retrieved from the repositories defined in Appendix A: . The *Notes* column specifies when the report corresponds to a custom build or if the code was retrieved from an alternate repository.

Benchmark	Variant Name	Branch	Commit	Notes
CHAMP	base	master	5f7d4c4ac5ed01f4aba9e0e73272233b8b3913cb	
CHAMP	dgemv			Custom made, derived from base
GAMMCOR	scemama	master	4638dfa61b8496c548f8d048eb5d2ac9d0fc082b	Retrieved from repository https://github.com/scemama/GAMMCOR.git
GAMMCOR	sokol			Handled by Adam Sokół
GAMMCOR	base	master	94bef26a28cb47ecad2a219a585010040ea054f	
GAMMCOR	Gammcor1-4	master	941e4a4161be57272f0655b5fed70695140e5852	
NECI	base	master	b1ad20173b38c71806f6f2ed53a7ca943a9b35e7	Version available on [11]

Benchmark	Variant Name	Branch	Commit	Notes
NECI	base	MAQAO_toggle	5cfcea7b77a94b9125d74088858a979aaf25a7b7	Version available on [12]
QMCHEM	base	master	2a68a494c42df6be81b588cbaf0740696d4cac3f	
QMCHEM	base	master	2a68a494c42df6be81b588cbaf0740696d4cac3f	NAME as QMCHEMINFO
QMCHEM	psidet1	psidet1	91f809b9737590581b0dc9025df4b2764de24d3a	NAME as QMCHEMINFO
QMCHEM	psidet2	psidet2	cdc925251793b64b38d9d27596131ddd273b939	NAME as QMCHEMINFO
TURBORVB	base	master	a08ea22de9099ad9be893ff39fcd766584628b8a	
TURBORVB	12march	master	bd7c01b2e968a1572d519ded2135648f96c9ffad	
TURBORVB	dgemv			Custom made based on 12march
TURBORVB	vectorization	vectorization	6d057f0c424a28a8842960007fd8b79a013b2e60	
TURBORVB	vectorization-dgemv	vectorization		Custom made based on vectorization
TURBORVB	miniapp			Custom made mini app based on makefun function
TURBORVB	01julymaster	master	bd7c01b2e968a1572d519ded2135648f96c9ffad	
TURBORVB	01julyvectorization	vectorization	12e39e46f54eca944318bcba4d50cd5e02a	

Benchmark	Variant Name	Branch	Commit	Notes
			caff4	
TURBORVB	05julyrefactorization	refactoring	0ee5400cf0eb787b1338d76fbd94ea482744b0c3	
TURBORVB	08julyrefactorization	refactoring	5a766d8c1d6eef620f974c9fb54297fc8aa7874e	
TURBORVB	31augnewrefactorization	new_refactoring	b7b956eb244e04d5b818c2c092b33413a511e459	

